

Fit-Gap Analysis Internal

Start of Block: Default Question Block

Background

Interviews are an essential part of Requirements Engineering. There are many types of interviews that can take place, depending on which stakeholders an analyst interacts with, the type of project or product, the development phase, the number of stakeholders that participate in an interview, and more. This survey is part of research on the importance of segments and categories in a specific type of interview.

The focus of this survey is **fit-gap analysis**, a type of interview in which an **existing software product** is discussed with the customer to assess whether the product **fits their requirements and processes or if there are gaps**. The illustration below shows the general process of a fit-gap analysis session.

Your tasks

First, you will be asked to **judge the importance of 16 selected quotes from industry recordings of fit-gap analyses**. Our data is based on the **software product SCANMAN**; if you see this name in the quotes, please keep in mind that this refers to the discussed product. For understandability, we have edited the quotes to convert domain abbreviations to full terms. Additionally, any information that could identify the customer has been omitted, abstracted, or paraphrased.

Second, after rating the quotes, you will be asked to **rank the relative importance of some categories** that we identified in our research.

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Disclaimer

This survey is related to research on fit-gap analysis. Therefore, in compliance with research ethics policies, we would like to give you the option to decide whether or not to allow your non-personal data to be used for research purposes.

Statistics generated from this survey - from the Likert scales and the ordering tasks of this survey - may be used in future publications in a completely anonymous way, paying attention to revealing no information that may disclose your identity. Furthermore, if you decide so, we may potentially reach out to you for further clarifications.

All data will be treated with the utmost confidentiality.

In case of any questions, please send an email to: tjerk@fizer.io (or) t.spijkman@uu.nl

My answers may be used to generate statistics, that may be used in publications

- Yes, feel free to use the answers I provide for publication purposes (1)
 - No, I would prefer if my answers are not included for this research. (2)
-

What is your experience with requirements elicitation / business analysis

- I have no experience with RE or business analysis (1)
 - I have taken a course or training on RE or business analysis (2)
 - I have practitioner experience on RE or business analysis (3)
-

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In this survey, we consider the notion of **importance for the goal of writing the analysis document**. After performing an analysis, the analyst needs to determine and document the fits and gaps discussed in the conversation.

You will rate 16 transcription fragments (all on this page of the survey), using the following scale, for their importance in documenting the fit-gap analysis: **Irrelevant**: information that should not be included in the document as it is not relevant to the configuration or customisation of the product. **Of little importance**: while not completely irrelevant, the information could be easily found elsewhere or is expected to have no impact on the configuration or customisation of the product. **Important**: information that is important for determining the configuration or customisation of the product. **Essential**: crucial information: if missing from the document, it negatively impacts the overall value of the document.

The statements are taken from industry cases for the software product SCANMAN. **SCANMAN is a tool that integrates with an enterprise resource planning (ERP) system to provide an automated processing of incoming invoices**. Additionally, it introduces approval flows through a workflow within the ERP system. Please view the video below to get an overall idea of the context of the segments.

To facilitate comprehension, **underlined domain terms in the statements are described in the mouseover tooltip**.

	Irrelevant (1)	Of little importance (2)	Important (3)	Essential (4)
<p>The IT department has their own ticketing system as well for IT related services, for example repairs that need to be done so they also have their own purchase orders. So theirs is not an <u>ERP purchase order</u>. (1)</p>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
<p>Basically what we do right now is we say, ok, I'm sending you this invoice. You have five days to tell me that there's a problem if I don't hear back from you in five days, I'm going to go pay it. I'm going to assume that it's ok. That's what we do right now. (2)</p>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
<p>I did like a quick analysis and I think mostly half of the invoices that come in will have <u>purchase orders</u> associated to them. (3)</p>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
<p>We still have a lot of invoices</p>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

that, especially in specific departments, go to the departments first. For example, facilities when they work with the construction companies. They deal directly with them and so they get all the invoices and what they do is they just send the accounts payable the invoices with approvals (4)

Some suppliers send us invoices, but also a spreadsheet. This spreadsheet breaks down the invoices per location. Which can be transformed and uploaded into our ERP. (5)

Because for a lot of these invoices, because as I said, they give us a statement by location. So we just print that statement. We don't print the invoices though as we have these electronically. (6)

There will be some exceptions that we will have. For example we will continue using two way match those invoices that describe intangible goods. (7)

For example, our electricity invoice can span a 100 to 200 pages. Within that it'll tell you for each location how much it is. We also get a spreadsheet with this breakdown by location. (8)

	Irrelevant (1)	Of little importance (2)	Important (3)	Essential (4)
In SCANMAN (software-product), is it by vendor that I can set if I want to <u>two way</u> or <u>three way match</u> invoices for this vendor? (1)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
For example, if we use the network folder, after it takes the invoice and reads it we can move it somewhere else right? (2)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Talking about invoices that are completely automated because it's automatically initiated you'll never see it. I don't think we should be worried about it, because it should follow the <u>purchase order</u> process that is set up right? (3)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
So if we're doing initial setup with <u>2 way match</u> and approval, at some stage we can change the settings to skip the approval right? (4)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

The system will automatically pick up the receipt to see if they match. So if the invoice comes in and a line item quantity is 10, and price is the same too. The distribution to accounts is then automatically done by the ERP, and when it doesn't match it will see that.

(5)

	Irrelevant (1)	Of little importance (2)	Important (3)	Essential (4)
We have offices in multiple European countries, including the Netherlands, Germany, France and Ireland. (1)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Our main office is responsible for processing the invoices of all our offices. So we have a centralised Accounts Payable department. (2)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
We receive approximately 25.000 invoices on a yearly basis. Most of these are through email, but approximately 5% are sent as physical copies. (3)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
We've seen a growth of approximately 50% in employees over the last 5 months. So we're expanding quickly and have been busy getting everyone up to speed. (4)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Our Accounts Payable (AP) department has 12 people working full-time. (5)

We have a template for the ERP that is used in all our locations. This can be slightly changed based on local requirements. (6)

	Irrelevant (1)	Of little importance (2)	Important (3)	Essential (4)
The main reason we're looking to SCANMAN (software-product) is not only to reduce amount of time it takes to enter invoices in the system, but also the approval process. (1)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
First of all, we can eliminate the need to manually enter invoices and get things out correctly and timely (2)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Everyone pretty much has it right, so there are very few mistakes. So the project is not for improving performance in the sense of avoiding errors. (3)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
We want to make our process all digital, and prevent printing everything out. (4)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
We've been on this journey to make our processes less manually focused, and move to more automation of	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

the processes.
(5)

	Irrelevant (1)	Of little importance (2)	Important (3)	Essential (4)
So how would you identify the location information now? Considering it is not included in the invoice. (1)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
How many different types of <u>purchase orders</u> do you currently have? (2)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I think we already covered that if it is <u>3-way match</u> , there is no approval needed right? (3)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
How are your approvals done currently? (4)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
So in this case, is there anything on the invoice that you currently use to know who to send it to? (5)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Could you repeat why we would want to have approval for some vendors, but not for others? (6)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Can SCANMAN set up different approval processes for different types of transactions or invoices? (7)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Can SCANMAN read an invoice statement like this one? (8)

Can SCANMAN read handwritten stuff? (9)

When they approve an invoice, they don't have an option to put a comment unless they're doing it from the ERP right? (10)

	Irrelevant (1)	Of little importance (2)	Important (3)	Essential (4)
If all goes well, half of the invoices should just run through the system match to the <u>purchase order</u> automatically. It should be seamless (1)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
As long as SCANMAN can make it easier for us in many ways, because we have a lot of standard invoices, then we're fine. (2)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
We need to ensure that SCANMAN works for our current process, and as we make changes to our processes to transition to work with our new processes. (3)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
What would be really good, is if we had in the email upon invoice rejection, the rejection reason could be selected. (4)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
We need to generate an invoice number based on specific logic. (5)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

What we're saying is; we want to select multiple invoices to batch process these. (6)

	Irrelevant (1)	Of little importance (2)	Important (3)	Essential (4)
<p>Hopefully with this whole new <u>purchase order</u> process that will change, right? Yeah, I know that we're going to have a lot of problems with the receiving in the beginning, 'cause it's a training issue, right? People need to get used to it. (1)</p>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
<p>So we're debating between whether we just let those come in and load, or do we just run the invoices through SCANMAN. I don't think we decided that yet, but we're leaning more towards just letting the invoices run through SCANMAN. (2)</p>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
<p>Let's see, we want to set up two different <u>escalation types</u> in the approvals. The first one would be to the next in line, so they don't get bottle-necked. Secondly, would be to the</p>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

manager so they know when employees are not doing their tasks. (3)

Janitorial and consultancy will be two-way match. Since it is a service, we don't need receiving. So then the system will read all the necessary information, but wait for us to say ok, process it. (4)

If there is an error, it should tell me why it was not processed. If it goes through three way match and fails, it will tell me why right? (5)

So the invoice comes in, it goes through the workbench and will enter whatever information it got from the OCR, but will it go for approval first, or will it tell me to enter the invoice first? (6)

And then there's the utility invoices, which are high in number of invoices and do

not require approval. How should we set those up? (7)

	Irrelevant (1)	Of little importance (2)	Important (3)	Essential (4)
<p>It's only because we're so big. We've been buying smaller offices, which is great because business is booming. But it also causes problems because we have to figure how to break it down and make it manageable (1)</p>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
<p>I can think of one department that I know they will want to look at the invoice. So we have to use approval even if the <u>purchase order</u> was already approved (2)</p>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
<p>Asking all our employees to confirm the received goods will add more work on their plate. So they will have to change their work, and we will have to convince them to do that. (3)</p>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
<p>Well, we have asked for a specific formatting of</p>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

invoices. But a vendor like this supplies pretty much all the electricity here. Which means they have to much leverage and don't need to adapt to our requests. (4)

Usually, our legal department is a bit difficult. They want this one thing, and are hard to convince. (5)

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Rank the following categories in the order which you think would provide the most value to an analyst, when statements regarding those categories appear in an interview or its transcript. 1 being the most valuable, and 8 being the least valuable.

- _____ Description or discussion of the current processes (as is situation) (1)
- _____ Description or discussion of the future processes with the software product (to be situation) (2)
- _____ Explicit discussion of certain requirements (3)
- _____ Provision of details about the customer organization (4)
- _____ Elaboration on the existing functionality of the software product (5)
- _____ Customer motivation for using or acquiring of software product (7)
- _____ Questions made by or to the analyst (8)
- _____ Explication of the reasons behind the challenges / problems in the organization (9)

If you have any additional comments or other things you would like to share, please enter these in the box below.

- Timing
- First Click (1)
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